

On Six Logics of Xi Jinping's Education Concept in the New Era

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Abstract: As the fundamental guarantee for the sustainable development of human society, education is the country's great plan and the party's plan. Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, the Party Central Committee with Comrade Xi Jinping has attached great importance to education, and has made a series of important arrangements for education. He has profoundly discussed "what kind of people, how to train people, and who to train people". Major theoretical and practical issues such as "What kind of education, how to run education, and for whom to run education" have enriched and developed the socialist education theory with Chinese characteristics, from political logic, value logic, theoretical logic, historical logic, and realistic logic. The six aspects of practical logic have comprehensively explained the socialist education with Chinese characteristics in the new era, and constitute a unified whole with internal logic.

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The concept of education is an understanding and view of educational phenomena and problems formed on the basis of educational practice under the influence and constraints of political, economic, and cultural social conditions in a certain historical era. Education in each era has a close connection with the society of this era. Since the Eighteenth National Congress of the CPC, the Party Central Committee

with Xi Jinping as the core has deeply grasped the laws and trends of the socialist education with Chinese characteristics, effectively based on the reform and practice of socialist education with Chinese characteristics, and accurately positioned the era characteristics of the development of socialist education with Chinese characteristics, Put forward a series of educational ideas that embody the CPC's purpose, are full of humanism, contain traditional heritage, based on strategic ideas, comprehensive multidimensional considerations, and show China's wisdom. From the perspective of ontology, value theory, epistemology, methodology, etc. we discuss the multi-dimensional construction of the socialist education concept with Chinese characteristics.

I. The Political Logic: "Governance for the People"-the purpose of serving the masses, which is the unity of the party's overall leadership and the people's satisfied education

The core task of the ruling party is to govern the country, which is essentially a political activity and must follow certain political logic. [] Building the party for the public and ruling for the people has always been the political logic and premise of the Chinese Communist Party in formulating lines, guidelines and policies. Strengthening the overall leadership of the party and adhering to the fundamental position of taking the people as the center are the compass

and the star of the constant development and advancement of the socialist education with Chinese characteristics in the new era. Strengthening the Party's overall leadership in education is to plan education, top-level design, plan optimization, and path selection from the overall level of national construction, the direction of social development, and the micro-level of personal growth, so as to manage the satisfaction of the people. Education is constantly improving the people's sense of gain from education, which is also the fundamental manifestation of the Marxist mass view and the purpose and requirement of the Communist Party of China to serve the people wholeheartedly. In this regard, Xi Jinping paid great attention. First, we must strengthen the Party's overall leadership over education. Adherence to the party's leadership in all work is reflected in the field of education, which is to implement normalized, professional, and specific party building management. He put forward, "Strengthening the Party's overall leadership over education is the fundamental guarantee for running a good education. Party committees at all levels should incorporate education reform and development into the agenda, and the main responsible comrades of the party and government must be familiar with education, care about education, and research education. Party organizations of various types of schools at all levels should regard the party building work of schools as the basic skills of running schools, and fully implement the party's education policies in all aspects of school work. " People's education is for the people, and running a satisfactory education for the people is the original intention of the Communist Party of China in the cause of education. Since the Eighteenth National Congress of the Communist Party of China, "Comrade Xi Jinping has presided over the meeting several times to discuss major education issues, visited the education system many times and issued a series of important speeches, further deepening our party 's understanding of the law of socialist education with Chinese characteristics, providing a fundamental follow for people 's satisfied education "[] He mentioned that "always put education at the strategic position of priority development,

continuously expand investment, strive to develop education for all, lifelong education, build a learning society, and strive to make every Each child has the opportunity to be educated and strives to make 1.3 billion people enjoy a better and fairer education and the ability to develop themselves, contribute to society, and benefit the people. "[] Third, we must adhere to the "four services" education policy. Regarding the guidelines for education, he proposed "four services", emphasizing the nationality, politics, and people's characteristics of socialist education with Chinese characteristics in the new era, and provided guidelines for the development of China's education, especially higher education. The organic unification of the CPC's management of education and education for the people has been realized, and the unification of Chinese characteristics and practical characteristics of education has been achieved. It pointed out that "China has a unique history, a unique culture, and a unique national condition. Education must be firm in its own way, serve the people, serve the Communist Party of China's governance of the country, consolidate and develop the socialist system of Chinese characteristics, serve Reform and opening up and socialist modernization services. "[]

II. The Value Logic: "People-oriented"-to foster virtue through education and quality education, people's free and comprehensive development of concern

The Communist Manifesto stated that all-round human development is the ideal goal of the communists and the basic principles of the communist society, and further pointed out that education is the only way to create all-round human development. [] This is also the process of achieving "human socialization". To become a talent, you need to be an adult; to be an adult, you must be virtuous. The way to educate people is to make virtue first. " to foster virtue through education" answered the question of whom shall be cultivated of the value theory, "Quality Education" answered the question

of how to cultivate the person's methodology, "Achieving the All-round Development of Man" answered the question of why the person was cultivated. The socialist education with Chinese characteristics in the new era is based on the principle of "to foster virtue through education" and "quality education" as the core, with the goal of consolidating people's hearts, improving personality, developing manpower, cultivating talents, and benefiting the people, and ultimately promoting human freedom and comprehensive development. In this regard, Xi Jinping discussed from the aspects of moral education and quality education, such as the main body, status, ways and contents. First, pay attention to the enlightenment and culture of family education. He values family education as the first stage of broad social education, and plays an important role in developing children's minds. He thinks "Family is the first class in life, and parents are the children's first teachers. There is just as much kind of tutor as there is. Family education involves many aspects, but the most important thing is moral education, the ducation of how to become a person. "[] " Tell the children the first lesson in life to help buckle the first button in life. The education, women's federation and other departments must coordinate social resources to support family education. "[] The second is to clarify school education as the dominant position. He has high expectations for the school, a highly specialized teaching organization. Put forward "I hope that the school will bear the sacred responsibility of building up morals, teaching and educating people." "[] "The strength of the country is due to people, and the talents are derived from learning.' It is our party's responsibility to train socialist builders and successors. The educational policy is the common mission of schools at all levels in China. "[] The third is to give play to the basic role of moral education. He emphasized the extreme importance of enhancing moral cultivation and strengthening character education, and regarded "to foster virtue through education" as the foundation of young students. He thinks that "the majority of young people are all a piece of jade, and they often use truth, goodness and beauty to sculpt themselves, and constantly cultivate noble conduct

and simple emotions, and strive to make themselves a noble person." "[] "The effectiveness of the "to foster virtue through education" should be regarded as Examine the fundamental standards of all work in the school, truly educate people with culture and morality, continuously improve students' ideological level, political consciousness, moral quality, and cultural literacy, and realize the virtues of virtue, ethics, and strict privacy are internalized to all fields, aspects, and links of university construction and management. "[] The fourth is to emphasize the cultural influence of traditional virtue education. He believes that traditional Chinese culture is the "root" and "soul" of the Chinese nation, and that traditional Chinese virtues are the "form" and "god" of contemporary people, so they should be nourished by traditional virtue education. It is proposed that "Chinese traditional virtue is the essence of Chinese culture and contains rich ideological and moral resources. Don't forget the original ability to open up the future, and be good at inheritance to innovate better." "[] "To learn the rules of being a person, we must learn and inherit the Chinese national traditional Virtue, study and promote the new socialist fashion, love life, know how to be grateful, be kind to others, and be honest and honest. "[] " Good teachers must have the dedication and self-consciousness of 'holding a heart without going with half a grass' Adhere to the spiritual homeland, adhere to the bottom line of personality, take the lead in promoting socialist morality and traditional Chinese virtues, and influence and drive students with their own exemplary behavior. "[] The fifth is to explain the core values of the times. He analyzed the dialectical relationship between core values and morals, and pointed out the practical path to practice core values. I think that "core values are actually a kind of virtue, both personal and a kind of virtue, that is, the virtue of the country and society. The country has no virtue, and people have no virtue. If a nation or a country has no virtue, The common core values, no one agrees, if you do not depend on it, then this nation and country will not be able to advance. "[] " We must effectively penetrate the socialist core values in all aspects of social life. Through education and guidance,

publicity, culture and practice Cultivation, system security, etc., internalize the core values of socialism into people's spiritual pursuits and externalize into people's conscious actions. "[] Sixth, highlight the cohesiveness of patriotism education. He explained the importance of patriotism education in establishing a common sense, promoting collective action, and inspiring national integrity. Demands to carry out in-depth, long-lasting and vivid patriotism propaganda and education among the young people, so that the spirit of patriotism is firmly rooted in the hearts of the young people, let the young people cultivate the feeling of patriotism, cultivate the ambition to strengthen the country, practice the trip to the country, and let the patriot The spirit of doctrine has been passed on from generation to generation and carried forward. "[]" We must strengthen patriotism, collectivism, and socialist education, guide the Chinese people to establish and adhere to the correct historical, national, and cultural views, and strengthen the spirit of being Chinese. Harmony. "[] Seventh, we attach importance to the comprehensive development of quality education. For quality education, he conducted a comprehensive interpretation of the various dimensions of ethics, morals, intelligence, physical, beauty, and labor. He believes that "youth must be diligent to learn and improve their comprehensive qualities, strive to achieve moral integrity and lofty ambitions, be diligent and self-motivated, pursue excellence, be strong in physique, healthy in mind and body, temper your will, and be tough." [] Work hard to strengthen ideals and beliefs, work hard to plant patriotism, work hard to strengthen moral character, work hard to increase knowledge, work hard to cultivate the spirit of struggle, work hard to enhance comprehensive quality, To comprehensively strengthen and improve school aesthetic education, we must promote the spirit of labor among students. "[]

III. Historical logic: "strategic decision"- the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation supported by the strategy

of rejuvenating the country through science and education and the strategy of strengthening the country with talents

Building a strong education nation is the basic project for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. From the New Democratic Revolution to the Socialist Revolution, Construction and Reform, from the "Four Modernizations" to the comprehensive construction of a well-off society, and from the Opium War to the 40th anniversary of reform and opening up, the great Chinese nation has been fighting hard and advancing on the road of rejuvenation. Especially since the Eighteenth National Congress of the Party, China's socialist economic construction, political construction, cultural construction, social construction and ecological civilization construction have been actively promoted, and new major progress has been made in the comprehensive construction of a well-off society. Asymptotic. National rejuvenation is inseparable from economic development, economic development is inseparable from scientific and technological progress, and scientific and technological progress is inseparable from talent education. The strategy of rejuvenating the country through science and education is a major decision made based on the scientific conclusion that "science and technology are the first productive forces." The two will inevitably become the basic guarantee for the prosperity of the country and the happiness and well-being of the people, and will also become the strategic support for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. General Secretary Xi Jinping has also discussed this. One is to solve the current situation of imbalance in education development. He insisted on starting from the reality of China's current education problems and pointed out the role of the two major strategies. It is proposed that "the current historical accumulation of various educational resources in China is insufficient, the development of education is uneven among regions, the overall educational conditions are not very satisfactory, the overall income level of teachers, especially grassroots teachers, is not high, the standard of schooling conditions

is not high, and the level of education management needs to be improved. This requires us to adhere to the strategy of rejuvenating the country through science and education and the strategy of strengthening the country with talents, insist on placing education at the strategic position of giving priority to development, and continue to vigorously promote the reform and development of education, so that our country's education will become better and stronger. "[] The second is the choice of the times to continuously improve the comprehensive national strength. He realized that education had a profound impact on the cultivation of talents and thus on the enhancement of national strength and development. It is believed that "competition of comprehensive national strength in today's world is, in the final analysis, competition for talents. Talents are becoming more and more a strategic resource for economic and social development, and the basic, pioneering, global status and role of education are more prominent." [] All regard running colleges and training talents as strategic measures to achieve national development and enhance comprehensive national strength. [] The third is the historical necessity of finally achieving national rejuvenation. He profoundly revealed the basic role, urgent requirements, and decisive significance of education for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. It is pointed out that "to achieve the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, the status and role of education cannot be ignored. Our need for education is more urgent than ever, and our desire for scientific knowledge and excellent talents is stronger than ever. Education is to improve the comprehensiveness of the people. Quality, an important way to promote the overall development of people, is an important cornerstone of national rejuvenation and social progress, and is a cause of decisive significance for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. The realization of the two hundred-year struggle goals and the Chinese nation 's great revival of the Chinese dream In the final analysis, it depends on talents and education. "[]

IV. Realistic Logic: "Dimensional Choice"-

Prioritize the development of educational undertakings that ensure the fairness of education and enhance the quality of education

Responding to the concerns of the times and solving practical problems are the actual starting point and ultimate goal of developing education. Significant changes have taken place in the main social contradictions of our country. When it comes to the field of education, it is an urgent need to focus on solving the growing demand for the contradiction between the diversification, individualization and quality of education services and education products of the people, and the imbalance from the development of education and the supply of services Accelerating the development of more equitable and higher-quality education has become a top priority. Educational equity is the meaning of social equity. However, ensuring education equity is not an end, but a guarantee to improve the quality of education. Both of these aspects should not be neglected. They are both consideration dimensions for achieving the priority of education development. Priority in the development of education must be regarded as important for promoting the development of the party and the country Go first. In this regard, Xi Jinping showed deep concern. One is to incorporate education equity into an important category of social equity. From the overall perspective of social equity, he conducted a comprehensive study and judgment on the premise, rank, and relationship with social equity of educational equity. It is proposed that "we must do our best to promote social equity and justice on the basis of continuous development, and strive to enable all people to learn from education, gain from labor, get sick from illness, and keep old. New progress has been made in the areas of fostering and living. "[] It is pointed out that education equity is an important foundation of social equity. It is necessary to continuously promote the development of education and achieve more fairness and benefit to all people, and promote social equity and justice with education equity. [] The second is to pay attention

to the development of education in poor and backward areas. He focused his attention on the "depressions" and "shortcomings" of China's education, making it clear that grasping education is the inevitable connection to poverty alleviation. It is emphasized that "the development of old revolutionary bases and poverty-stricken areas must basically focus on education, and do not let children lose at the starting line. Financial funds should be inclined in this regard." [] "To help the poor people improve their physical and cultural qualities. , *Employability?*, strive to prevent poverty due to illness, return to poverty due to illness, open a solid channel for children to change their fate through multi-channel employment through learning and growth, and young adults to firmly prevent the intergenerational transmission of poverty. "[] The third is to indicate that education is an important way of fairness. Starting from the path of jointly building and sharing educational resources, he explored the possibility of achieving urban-rural equity, regional equity and inter-generational equity in education. It is proposed that "through education informatization, the digital gap between regions and urban and rural areas will be gradually reduced, education equality will be vigorously promoted, and hundreds of millions of children will share quality education under the blue sky and change fate through knowledge" we strive to develop education for all and life-long education, build a learning society, strive to allow every child to have access to education, and strive to enable 1.3 billion people to have a better and fairer education, gain the ability to develop themselves, contribute to society, and benefit humanity . "[] The fourth is to focus on creating a good educational environment. The development of education is inseparable from the objective environment of relative freedom, openness, inclusiveness, and enterprising. For the shaping of the environment, he emphasized that "we must deepen education reform, promote quality education, innovate education methods, improve the quality of talent cultivation, and strive to form a conducive environment to the growth of innovative talents. "Education environment for people." [] "We will uphold the concept that technology is

the first productive force and talents are the first resources, eclectic , absorb advanced international experience, promote educational reform, improve the quality of education, and train more higher-quality talents. At the same time provide a wider world for all kinds of talents to play their roles and display their talents. "[] The fifth is to emphasize the need to follow the laws of education. Because the law of education development and the law of talent growth are objective, scientific and reasonable, it is more necessary to run education according to the law. He proposed "to absorb the world's advanced experience in running schools, and to follow the law of education and take root in China's land to run universities. "[]" We must improve the personnel training mechanism in accordance with the law of talent growth, 'shun the sky, so that its nature', to avoid rushing for quick gains and promoting seedlings. "[] Six is to specify the principle of evaluating the quality of education. The quality of education requires evaluation standards. He raised the basic principles of measuring the quality of education to the historical level of promoting the continuous development of human civilization. He proposed that "we must actively develop education, through universal education, enlighten the mind, pass on knowledge, cultivate emotions, Better understand the value of various civilizations through continuous knowledge-giving, and let education serve the inheritance and creation of civilizations. "[]

V. Theoretical logic: "Critical Inheritance" —— Construction of Modern Educational Ideas Blending Western Educational Philosophy with Chinese Educational Tradition

Combing the historical evolution of Chinese and Western educational philosophy, we can see the different ideas and explorations of education by ancient and modern philosophers and thought masters at home and abroad. These are undoubtedly valuable theoretical resources for observing

and thinking about educational issues in the new era, and are also the construction and expansion of modern education. The main source of ideas. Xi Jinping emphasized not only the reasonable elements of learning and borrowing from Western educational thoughts, but also special attention to maintaining and promoting the background connotation of traditional educational culture, which reflected the inclusiveness of education thought orientation and the uniqueness of value inheritance. One is the choice of Western education philosophy. The development of western educational ideas generally follows the following historical context: service politics (the pursuit of value in ancient Greek educational philosophy)-to the upper level (utilitarian concepts of ancient Roman educational philosophy)-restraining people and raising gods (religious characteristics of medieval educational philosophy)- —Pushing up human nature (the spiritual outlook of humanistic educational philosophy) — Practicing the world (basic nature of realist educational philosophy) —Development instinct (pursuing the goal of naturalistic educational philosophy) —Educational omnipotence (materialistic educational philosophy the clear stand)-social progress (historical responsibility of progressive education philosophy)-longing for eternity (the lofty concept of conservative education philosophy)-meaning of life (existence of philosophy of existential education)-scientific methods (analysis Standard pursuit of educational philosophy)-critical reality (the deconstruction of the paradigm of postmodernist educational philosophy). Xi Jinping reasonably absorbed and used the "core" of western education philosophy to promote science, pursue human nature, observe reality, serve society, and sublimate life, especially the Marxist educational concept on the realization of human free and comprehensive development. "Absorb all the outstanding civilization achievements created by mankind with a broad perspective, insist on keeping abreast of the reforms, constantly surpassing ourselves, and in the process of opening up to learn from others, and constantly improve ourselves." [] The second is to rationally surpass the educational and cultural traditions. Ancient Chinese

education often attached importance to the political function of education, the example of the monarch, and the moral role of art. Its main characteristics are that it emphasizes worldliness over divinity, morality over utility, government over nature, harmony over competition, and the whole. The characteristics of valuing individuals and accumulating more than creating more reflect the secular spirit, moral spirit, harmonious spirit, group spirit and humanistic spirit. On the whole, it has a strong color of education ethics. [] Under the collision and exchange of Chinese and Western educational ideas, modern Chinese education has produced many educational ideas and practices such as Westernization Education, Reformation Education, Personality Education, Vocational Education, Civilian Education, Rural Education, Life Education, Living Education, and Revolutionary Education. [] China's contemporary education, especially after the reform and opening up, puts more emphasis on the development direction of quality education, subject education, innovation education, equality education and lifelong education. [] Therefore, in sorting out the ins and outs of the development of the history of Chinese educational thought, critically absorbing the essence that meets the economic and social objective conditions of the new era, such as "gezhihengcheng", "Xiuqizhiping", "Heaven and man unite" On the basis of "harmonious coexistence" and "practical experience", a historical gene for the concept of socialist education with Chinese characteristics in the new era has been formed. The third is the systematic construction of modern educational ideas. The educational concept of the new era is precisely constructed using Marxist dialectics and historical views of materialism, after absorbing and drawing on the essence of ancient and modern Chinese and foreign educational ideas. On the cognitive level, the modern educational concept has changed the characteristics of the previous education that stresses the importance of examination and application, breaks through the experience-oriented constraints, is more systematic in content, more targeted, and is endowed with a humanistic spirit, pioneering spirit and critical spirit. The ideological connotation shows

the characteristics of objectivity, credibility, science, and rule of law; on the operational level, the modern educational concept has changed the characteristics of previous education of emphasized theory rather than practice, and is more mature and rational in guiding educational activities. It has been endowed with ideological contents such as reform spirit, practical spirit, and innovative spirit, showing the characteristics of inclusiveness, feasibility, continuity, and transcendence, greatly enhancing the penetrating power, creativity, and vitality of contemporary educational ideas.

VI. Practical logic: "Two-wheel drive"- Deepen educational reform and expand educational openness

China's educational practice is deeply rooted in China's actual national conditions. From Premier Zhou Enlai's proposal to realize the "four modernizations" of socialism in 1964, to Comrade Deng Xiaoping's "three orientations" in 1983, and to the 2010 education planning outlines the goal of "basically realize education modernization by 2020", education modernization has always been Socialism education with Chinese characteristics is the goal to be fulfilled. Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, General Secretary Xi Jinping, with his broad global vision and profound historical vision, has demanded to take root in China, integrate Chinese and foreign countries, base on the times and face the future, and develop modern education with Chinese characteristics and world level. The 19th National Congress of the People's Republic of China put forward the grand goal of comprehensively building a powerful socialist modernization country and advanced the basic goal of socialist modernization by 15 years. This urgently requires that education be given priority in development and strengthening education first, with education modernization supporting the country's modernization and education strong country Socialist modern power. And "deepening educational reform" and "expanding educational opening"

are like two wheels of a car and two wings of a bird, constantly pushing us to explore the ideal of pursuing the goal of a strong education country. In response, Xi Jinping made several requirements. First, we must earnestly deepen the reform of the education system. Reform is a powerful driving force for social development and an inexhaustible engine for educational development. He believes that "education reform must adhere to cultural self-confidence, good experience must be adhered to, and shortcomings must be complemented. It is necessary to deepen reforms in the school management system, management system, funding system, examination enrollment and employment system, and deepen the school's internal management system and personnel reforms in the salary system, teaching management system, etc., and deepening reforms in talent training models, teaching content and methods have made education at all levels more in line with the law of education and the law of talent growth. Serving economic and social development capabilities, adjusting and optimizing the university's regional layout, discipline structure, and professional settings, establishing and improving the dynamic adjustment mechanism of disciplines and specialties, accelerating the construction of first-class universities and first-class disciplines, promoting collaborative innovation in production, education, and research, and actively implementing innovation-driven development strategies, focusing on cultivation of Innovative, compound, and applied talents. "[] Second, we must pay more attention to the construction of teachers. Teachers are the main force in the reform and development of education, as well as the practitioners of educational ideology and theory. He put forward the level standards of "good teachers" for the construction of the teaching staff. Demands that "the majority of teachers across the country should be good teachers with ideals, beliefs, moral sentiments, solid knowledge, and kindness, and make more changes for the development of modern education with Chinese characteristics and world-class standards, and for the cultivation of socialist cause builders and successors Great contribution. "[] He also clarified the role of" good

teacher ". "Teachers do the work of spreading knowledge, spreading ideas, spreading truth, shaping the soul, shaping life, and shaping people. Teachers should not only be book-teachers who teach book knowledge, but to become students' character, character, teachers and taste Mr. Da '. "[] Third, we must further strengthen Sino-foreign education cooperation and exchanges. He believes that the world's first-class educational resources should be connected through the platform established, promote each other, and continuously promote the development of China's education. It pointed out that "China will strengthen educational exchanges with countries around the world, expand the opening of education to the outside world, and actively support the development of education in developing countries." [] "It is necessary to conduct high-level cooperation in running schools with world-class resources." [] "To establish multi-level humanities Cooperation mechanism, build more cooperation platforms, and open up more cooperation channels. We must promote education cooperation, expand the scale of exchange of international students, and enhance the level of cooperation in running schools. "[] Fourth, we must widely absorb outstanding foreign educational achievements. He believes that foreign expert talents and national talents studying abroad should be actively introduced to achieve "going out, going back, drawing in, and retaining". It is proposed to "actively introduce outstanding overseas talents, formulate a more active international talent introduction plan, and attract more overseas innovative talents to work in China." [] "Study abroad should adapt to the general development of the country and the overall situation of the Party and the country, and plan to study abroad He came to China to study abroad, integrated the use of both international and domestic resources, cultivated more outstanding talents, worked hard to create a new situation in studying abroad, and constantly made new ideas for the realization of the "two hundred years" struggle goal and the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. Greater contribution. "[] The fifth is to strive to develop a modern education with Chinese characteristics and reach the world level. Education

can not be incomplete, but it can be based on the local characteristics of China; it cannot be foreign, but it can refer to world-class standards. This is the dialectics of education, and it is also the materialism of education. He pointed out that "the steady flow of human resources is an important potential force and latecomer advantage of China in the fierce international competition. I hope that the majority of teachers will understand the mission and responsibilities they shoulder and strive to develop modern education with Chinese characteristics and world level The builders and successors of the socialist cause have made greater contributions. "